

Customer Resource Management: Computerized change and Manageable Plan of Action Development

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ABSTRACT

The take-off point for this analysis is the comprehension of client relationship the board (CRM) as a bunch of innovative arrangements key for productive business the executives, the advantages of which, featured by past works, are introduced and characterized here as urgent for enterprising achievement. Exceptionally compelling for this intention are the current examinations on manageability, which give a feasible exploration model to survey and approve the expected impact of each CRM part (deals, promoting, and benefits) on the three components of maintainability (monetary, natural, and social). Endless supply of our theories, the ensuing approval of such model ought to bring a superior comprehension of the manner by which CRM-related advantages might build the positive effect of its segments on each element of manageability. CRM can henceforth be viewed as a kind of Green IT, situated toward advanced change and supportable plan of action development. Surely, this examination model might be the reason for a more explicit approach to gauge the effect and advantages of applying CRM, comprehended, as we will battle, both as far as practical plans of action and advancement.

Key words: Business model innovation, economic, social and environmental sustainability, sustainable business model, Customer interaction and client information, monetary development, integrational approach

INTRODUCTION

This paper proposes an examination model to investigate how client relationship the board (CRM) brings little and medium endeavors (SMEs) a double advantage, as far as both client information the executives (CKM) and advancement European Commission [1]. This juncture of interests and advantages is a central issue to consider CRM a basic apparatus for plan of action development, driving SME endeavors toward monetary, social and natural maintainability. Generally, SMEs have been the foundation of the European economy, including more than almost 100% of every single European organization, and 66% of the private-area occupations. Consequently the effect of CRM on SMEs is of unique interest given the social and monetary significance of this area [2].

Client information the executives and advancement are the two key present day firm drivers for a bunch of fruitful endurance, development, and improvement methodologies, upgrading business productivity, execution, and practical upper hand. Undoubtedly, information has been characterized as the main vital asset for, and surprisingly the center component of economical upper hand. Nonaka and Takeuchi [3] contend that both advancement and intensity require information. As result, Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) further express that information and development are basic and indistinguishable. In this sense, working Customer Knowledge Management through community advancement shows a proficient way for information sharing, and along these lines, effective development rehearses [4]. In fact, Polanyi M. [5] comprehend client joint effort as a cutting-edge anchor of client information the board and advancement, just as a framework empowering effective associations to gain from their clients' necessities how to fulfill their needs and further develop execution [3]. This call to solidifying and coordinating client joint effort and client need information is the thing that CRM looks to react to as both an essential device and business reasoning for driving firms.

CRM arose during the 1970s (Borgogni L., [6]) as another device for overseeing and streamlining deals power robotization inside organizations. Eversince, it has gotten quite possibly the most mainstream devices for big business data the executives, for deals and showcasing purposes, yet in addition for more powerful Customer Interaction and client information the board, just as for the comprehension of authoritative conduct. Aggarwal, S. [7] characterize client relationship the board as a mix of cycles, human resources and innovation looking for the most ideal comprehension of

an organization's clients. Also, on the off chance that we place our emphasis especially on client maintenance and relationship the board, CRM is the latest integrational approach accessible for relationship the executives.

A firm willing to endure and advance its situation in the market needs to dominate both in its shady and exploratory development [8], in spite of the authoritative pressures coming about because of the two patterns. Such blend of current double-dealing and planned investigation is the guideline for practical plans of action as the center of present day and dynamic organizations. In this light, the interest of the current investigation is clear: it expects to demonstrate CRM a proficient mechanical answer for help organizations in the current double-dealing of their assets, just as to investigate and advance in all spaces prompting maintainable monetary and monetary development.

The aftereffects of this exploration model, applied to a particular organization, will show the effect of sending and utilizing client relationship the board, both as far as client information the executives and development. The design of this paper starts with a writing audit rotating around the idea of CRM and its advantages. It is through these underlying readings, harping on the advanced idea of CRM and its effect on unique firms, deciphered both as mechanical and hierarchical change, that we have perceived the need to direct further research on the two principle factors of able to use both hands associations: client information the board (as the abuse cycle), and development (the investigation interaction). The two regions will appropriately be considered and inspected as secluded provisions, yet in addition in their particular relationship to CRM.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The underlying piece of our writing audit pinpoints both the idea and recognized advantages of CRM, subsequently establishing the frameworks for future exploration trying to quantify the effect of CRM on key business markers.

The second piece of such audit is then fixated on two vital factors of able to use both hands associations, the first being client information the executives, a center part of the abuse cycle. Here, the connection between client information the executives and CRM ought to likewise be considered since it could decide the genuine advantages of carrying out CRM in organizations.

The second fundamental variable associated with our survey is advancement, investigated in mix with CRM as an expertise with immediate and important effect on the last mentioned. Development has demonstrated the most applicable measurement when working with CRM as key device to achieve feasible plans of action, basic as it very well might be to guarantee the imminent manageability and increment of its exceptional related advantages.

CRM: concept and benefits

Client relationship the board contains a bunch of programming devices uncommonly conceived to order the three tomahawks of firm-client relations [9]: deals, advertising, and administrations [5].

Indeed, Scullin, Allora, Lloyd, and Fjermestad [10] express that electronic CRM has become the most recent worldview in the realm of client relationship the board, as present day organizations have perceived the need to develop in a climate delicate way to prevail with their advertising methodologies. Since its development, CRM has had the universally acknowledged, essential objective of both drawing in and holding financially important clients, while leaving the less productive ones to the side [11]. Thinking about the straightly developing interest in CRM since the 1970s, they have thought of it as quite possibly the main spaces of study for applied sciences soon. In this day and age, with online market exchange continually developing, it's gotten basic to accumulate, dissect and measure all client information that SMEs might have the option to gather to transform first-time online buyers into faithful clients. Such test is highlighted by an investigation from the Boston Consulting Group, showing that 65% of online clients making a first-time buy on a given site won't ever buy again from it. On his part, Sims [12] has shown that CRM is an entirely important instrument for web-empowered organizations to fill the help hole deterring clients from buying once again on a similar online outlet after a first time.

CRM upgrades an organization's ability to facilitate showcasing and administration techniques in the method for coming to and holding long haul associations [6]. Since the fundamental vital objectives of every association incorporate long haul development and maintainability [13], the need to satisfy client needs a lot, just as to further develop consumer loyalty is viewed as the principle CRM target [14]. In this sense, Joo [15] has expressed that a client focused center is key for business achievement in the advanced market world, its fundamental rule being that a decent CRM technique can be reached by improving client faithfulness.

The execution and utilization of CRM in SMEs gets immediate advantages terms of both monetary execution and every day business movement. As such, enhancements in the general client experience lead to more noteworthy consumer loyalty, which thusly positively affects the organization's benefit [16], with the accompanying specific additions: expanded client reliability; a more powerful promoting methodology; further developed client assistance and backing; more prominent proficiency; and cost decrease.

With respect to Loyalty, CRM permits organizations to concentrate and incorporate both their exchange records and client information, making this data open and reasonable to all vital partners to distinguish the loyalest clients [17] and the best promoting exercises. Waltner [18] considers personalisation programming devices as one of the critical components for expanded client steadfastness. Without a doubt, in the present exceptionally aggressive market biological system there is a growingly basic requirement for SMEs to enhance the danger of losing significant clients.

Promoting turns out to be more powerful when firms send CRM because of the profoundly nitty gritty client data accumulated through connection. This data permits client dynamic expectation, which converts into more compelling and customized showcasing lobbies for effective organizations, with a higher effect on their deals and benefit. Indeed, Rong, Wang, and Liao [19] have contended that client data can work with client division and along these lines put forth advertising attempts more successful, on the grounds that gathering clients as per their market needs permits organizations to arrive at target bunches through fragment custom-made promoting endeavors.

Client assistance and Support is another market include subject to improvement through CRM, empowering an exhaustive comprehension of purchaser needs, and thus prompting better methods of meeting them. In reality, CRM can improve on an organization's far off cycles of request gathering, update, and position. Then again, CRM permits it to keep a continuous register of task speculation, including materials, costs, and time utilization. At long last, it offers admittance to a client support understanding data set. These upgraded capacities are coordinated to keep clients precisely where they should be: at the focal point of the organization's procedure [20].

CRM is important for a more extensive, information mining set of the executives programming apparatuses and arrangements. In this manner, it works with information investigation to discover definite, market-important data for more effective dynamic cycles [21]. In addition, incorporating all data in a solitary data set permits the entirety of the organization's partners to dispose of deceiving information, just as to have a predictable and brought together wellspring of data, a vital component to further develop effectiveness, decrease any costs identified with information access, investigation, and abuse, and subsequently arrive at better promoting choices. CRM contains programming or innovation, yet additionally essential information, which makes it a worldwide answer for more precise information investigation and better business choices [22].

CRM and customer knowledge management

Overseeing client information, fundamental for what it's worth for SMEs, depends on two explicit vital assets: client information the executives (CKM henceforth) and client direction (CO). Fidel et al. [23] contend that Innovation Orientation (IO) typically works as a fundamental, exceptionally powerful arbiter among CO and CKM. Both client cooperation and advancement direction plainly affect CKM and on the association's promoting results, which drives us to think of them as key variables to further develop business execution through the flawlessness of client information. CKM is likewise a significant vital asset with an extensively certain effect on advertising activities, in any event, exceeding that of Innovation Orientation [24]. In our view, this shows the significance of carrying out composed systems to increment collected client information.

CKM is in this manner a mix of authoritative instruments, rehearses, and delicate abilities focussed on the best way to make, collect and move client related information. Since the SMEs' standard absence of human resources limits their inward drive of information, CKM turns into an essential asset to make client esteem. Chua and Banerjee [25] consider the aggregation of both general information and CKM one of the fundamental elements working on upper hand in this kind of firms. Consequently, the connection among CKM and advancement has illustrated a serious new space of study, offering an incredible chance to create and expound these ideas and their effect, both on business greatness, and all the more quite on the increment of SME upper hand. A few investigations have been led with respect to the effect of CKM on business and undertakings. All the more as of late, Fidel et al. [23] have examined its impact on business development capacities.

The current globalization patterns request that driving organizations take up new aggressive difficulties, highlighting the need to zero in on overseeing client connections, and particularly on consumer loyalty as the primary method to endure and expand incomes. These advanced difficulties have urged driving firms to take on another, client focused direction, customer-centric knowledge management at the core of the purported relationship promoting, which infers a development from the value-based direction of conventional showcasing to the cutting edge discipline's attention on a social one. Social promoting fixates advertising endeavors on creating and supporting long haul relations with clients through a constant improvement of client support, conveying a high effect on consumer loyalty [26].

Driving associations depend on CRM programming frameworks to follow and break down client related data since their relations with clients can be incredibly improved by utilizing Information Technology (IT). Customisation is the substance of a client focused direction of showcasing procedure, and it tends to be reached by conveying and adjusting CRM to client needs and particularities. CRM tries to extend client related information, just as it urges its successful use to direct customers' buy encounters, income development and benefit. CRM is likewise viewed as an advantaged the board approach focused on the distinguishing proof, fascination, further turn of events and retainment of fruitful client relations, at last committed to expanding productive client reliability [27]. Fruitful firms have found how to effectively drive their advertising endeavors by focusing on clients producing high incomes rather than dormant or unimportant ones, which makes client customized procedures essential. CRM empowers organizations to send such systems by overseeing singular client relations with the help of client information bases and intelligent, mass customisation advancements. An adequate and consistently refreshed client information is basic for a compelling CRM framework, CRM has unquestionably evolved solid binds with the discipline of client information the board [28].

CRM and innovation

Advancement is characterized as a bunch of thoughts, practices, or articles apparent as momentous by either an individual or a gathering of individuals. Advancement capacities allude to an association's utilization of innovation in the method for creating spearheading frameworks, approaches, programming, items, cycles, gadgets, or administrations. Such capacities likewise incorporate an organization's capacity to absorb and use outside information to acquire achievement situated information and business data [29].

SMEs can work on their CKM through two principle factors: client direction (CO from now on) and advancement direction (IO in the future). An incorporated and adjusted way to deal with CKM and CO practices is totally basic for a fruitful CRM sending, the two factors being fundamental assets for the organization. When reliably incorporated and treated as a worldwide technique, these three assets (CKM, CO and IO) may work on the SMEs' abilities, like their advancement abilities, just as work on their outcomes, for example in showcasing terms, while holding their upper hands [30].

Menguc and Auh [31] believe IO to be a hierarchical asset, similarly adding to expanding and keeping up with upper hand. On their part, Hult, Hurley, and Knight [32] think about IO as a critical factor to accomplish effective organizations. At long last, driving job in SME accomplishment as advancement focused execution permits organizations to work on their seriousness through a direction shift.

Advancement measures are the main component for a creative framework [23]. Advancement assists organizations with working on their presentation by empowering them to make, survey and foster novel and helpful items, administrations and practices, thus making and holding an incentive for interior and outside partners, and creating new types of revenue [33].

Hierarchical development is especially basic for SMEs, and particularly for little firms. To take advantage of the current market openings, the last need to keep straight with the continually developing client needs, and this requires certain advancement abilities. Soliman, H. S. [34] think about this as a critical component to accomplish upper hand.

In a period of persistent change, where items, cycles and administrations are continually advancing to adjust market worth to client needs and market requests, producers and specialist co-ops need to improve their advancement capacities to support upper hand. In reality, the present profoundly unusual, changing client needs must be met by effective organizations through item and administration advancement. Consequently, CRM works with an association's social occasion, examination, and double-dealing of information identified with client needs and inclinations, appreciating as it does wide acknowledgment for boosting development and guaranteeing long haul upper hand [35].

Ru-Jen, Chen, and Chiu [36] have pinpointed the impacts of a few CRM measurements on development abilities. For this reason, CRM is portrayed as containing five unique measurements (data sharing, client association, long haul organization, joint critical thinking, and innovation based CRM), and their connected development abilities: item advancement, measure development, managerial development, showcasing development, and administration development. Item advancement is characterized as the turn of events and dispatch, both of new items in general, or of weighty capacities, quality, consistency or appearance for existing items. Interaction advancement alludes to any changes underway cycles spearheading more useful frameworks for great assembling or administration arrangement. Showcasing development understands all techniques empowering more effective client focusing on tasks (statistical surveying, division, and data frameworks; value setting procedure; publicizing efforts), as characterized. On their part, Gopalakrishnan and Damanpour [37] describe administration development as the advanced makers' developing commitment with further developed consumer loyalty, after-deals administrations, ensure approaches, upkeep schedules, and request arrangement frameworks. Regulatory advancement is perceived as a bunch of exercises including changes in authoritative designs or managerial cycles, for example, human asset strategies for enrollment and portion, task meeting and prize approaches. Advancement underway and IT measures favors an able to use both hands execution, though changes in coordinations frameworks, notwithstanding being positive, are less important.

Each organization shows differentiating levels of CRM improvement and order, which drives us to foresee a differential, CRM-related effect on every development capacity. The most clear CRM impact, with beneficial outcomes in every one of the five sorts of development, comes from innovation based drives. Notwithstanding, it might therefore be contended that not all CRM exercises add to development programs emphatically. Along these lines, there is a solid need to enhance CRM with different components, like provider data.

RESULTS

After a comprehensive writing survey, that most existing investigations have effectively portrayed the advantages of CRM execution on firm execution. In any case, a merged way to deal with the previously mentioned, double-dealing investigation duality of present and future CRM benefits remains undertheorized. Taking these bifold benefits as a beginning stage, the current paper means to introduce an examination strategy pointed toward deciding if CRM is to be sure a mechanical arrangement inside the extent of maintainability and supportable plans of action.

Advantage guides of CRM in the present and what's to come

To sum up our finishing up comments from the past hypothetical conversation, the accompanying guide (Figure 1) addresses the advantages expected of CRM execution, both as far as current double-dealing (client information the board), and planned investigation (development):

Fig. 1 CRM benefit map

According to a compositional point of view, CRM involves three unique viewpoints: deals, showcasing, and administrations. Worked mutually, these three apparatuses pursuit the fundamental goal of conceiving a powerful CRM methodology, empowering client unwaveringness improvement [38].

CKM (client information the board) alludes to authoritative execution, and, all the more explicitly, to the at present detectable, CRM-related arrangement of advantages, though advancement makes reference to the planned, benefits expected because of contributing on measure improvement.

In this sense, our writing survey has additionally revealed insight into the shortfall of viewpoints straightforwardly relating CRM to supportability, just as on the absence of interest seeing the double-dealing investigation mix as a bifold pattern for reasonable turn of events.

Research Model

The past research holes plainly highlight the requirement for a bunch of methodological standards permitting us to draw associations between all CRM-related advantages, momentum and future, and a feasible plan of action ensuring its drawn out financial, social, and ecological effectiveness.

While leaving from the recognized advantages of CRM for SMEs, this paper likewise expects to determine if CRM could be viewed as an anchor of manageability among the diverse mechanical arrangements accessible for big business the executives. In the accompanying areas, provides perusers a few theories upon the effect of CRM execution on the three principle measurements contained by normal feasible plans of action. The exploration model proposed in this paper might be utilized whenever, in any area or offered organization, to decide how CRM sending can support a reasonable plan of action.

Sustainability and CRM

The World Commission on Environment and Development [39] characterizes supportability as the 'advancement that addresses the issues of the present without compromising the capacity of people in the future to address their own issues'. Its three fundamental measurements, otherwise called the 'triple main concern', are the accompanying: monetary, natural, and social. Monetary maintainability happens when an equilibrium has been reached between the quest for financial execution and its feasible turn of events. Ecological supportability identifies with the impact of an association's business cycles, exercises, and procedure on its regular habitat, this impact being either certain or negative. At long last, social supportability empowers a strong association among business and society for a manageable turn of events. At the end of the day, a mutually advantageous arrangement is looked for with this last measurement.

Proposed Model

The ebb and flow area presents our overall exploration model, pointed toward deciding how the advantages of CRM arrangement might add to help diverse supportability factors, as outlined in Figure 2.

Our withdrawing theories allude to the effect that the execution and utilization of the three CRM modules (deals, promoting, and benefits) may bear on the three supportability centers: financial, natural, and social. After a predictable, CRM-themed writing survey, and given the shortfall of direct references connecting CRM with Sustainability, we have

inferred that a potential exploration interest might lie behind such nonappearance. As per our view, the aggregate sum of associations with be drawn from the three significant CRM segments (deals, advertising, and administrations) converts into nine distinct speculations managing center parts of business maintainability.

Fig. 2 Proposed research model.

CONCLUSION

This investigation has imagined and contrived an exploration model to experimentally approve the impacts of the three CRM segments (deals, showcasing, and administrations) on client information the executives and advancement, just as on the organizations' endeavors toward computerized change and supportable plan of action development. For this reason, we've taken as a beginning stage the CRM-advantage map delineated above, involving two distinct ways: a bunch of current-double-dealing designs for authoritative execution, in addition to an explorative one for forthcoming advancement, driving the way to a practical plan of action for what's to come. Our examination model has been developed as per every likely blend between the three CRM modules and the three manageability measurements (monetary, natural, and social).

Organizations, and especially little and medium-size ones (SME), will upgrade their information handling potential through the reception of effectiveness and achievement situated advances and arrangements. CRM is one of the cutting edge data frameworks (IS) accessible in the method for giving business leaders (BDM) with significant business information, particularly concerning the three CRM-related regions: deals, showcasing, and administrations. Hence, the objective of this present paper's examination model is to set up a construction and a progression of conceivable speculations appropriate to a future exact investigation for approving the impacts of CRM-segment effect on the three manageability measurements.

Endless supply of such theories, the ensuing approval of this model might add to our comprehension of the interaction whereby CRM-related advantages empower a positive, upgrading connection between's each CRM segment and every maintainability measurement. In this light, CRM should be viewed as a particular typology of Green IT for computerized change and maintainable plan of action development.

With respect to CRM-advantage map, and the principal principle variable, client information the board, four different factors should be recognized as bearing a pertinent effect on business results, the estimation of which should be tended to in a more explicit examination model. Thinking about the impact of such factors on business markers, and the manner in which CRM permits their satisfaction as beneficial objectives, our exploration model may experimentally show how CRM assists firms with prevailing through a reliable and all around organized client information the executives system. A first, positive result is the increment of client reliability, the viability of which depicts a client focused, and thusly effective firm on the grounds of social advertising standards. A second gainful impact lies on the improvement of advertising technique adequacy, since CRM might furnish interior promoting partners with key data to design out and choose the best missions and showcasing activities for client focusing on. A further developed client assistance and backing is the third CRM-related advantage, straightforwardly associated with the administrations region, and a vital factor to guarantee an organization's holding of its best clients through an effective, target-maintenance procedure dependent on an improved post-deals client experience. Ultimately, a fourth related benefit lies in the advancement of effectiveness boosting and cost-reductive capacities, given the requirement for an enduring organization to adjust its

business, showcasing and administration endeavors to specific objectives and explicit client highlights, subsequently balancing its proposal on the grounds of a practical view of market interest, and making productivity and progress. In respect with the second way of our advantage map, spinning around the advancement variable, five center tomahawks have been thought of: item, measure, regulatory, advertising, and administrations. Each of the five depict how organizations drive their endeavors toward a compelling speculation on the upgrade of both inside and outside business measures. In this sense, an observational approval of our proposed research model might permit specialists to measure the effect of every hub on the turn of events and execution of spearheading and proficient deals, promoting, and administration approaches.

In spite of the general scholarly and business commitments of this examination, a few restrictions should likewise be recognized. In the first place, the exploration model spread out in these pages is a general, essential one, to be enhanced with certain appraisal markers, permitting model approval inside explicit areas and business conditions. Second, while this examination comprehends CRM as the mix of three principle parts (deals, promoting, and benefits), it has not thought about some second-level, conceivably nearby or frill components. Third, each CRM segment has been managed in a normalized, and subsequently practically identical profundity, henceforth leaving to the side the contrasts between each CRM supplier or potentially producer.

At last, as far as future examination lines, this model could be explained into a more explicit procedure, fit for some random area and additionally endeavor norms, to approve and observationally evaluate the impact of each CRM system on an organization's overall business results.

REFERENCE

- [1]. European Commission. (2013). One trillion euro to invest in Europe's future—The EU's budget framework 2014–2020.
- [2]. <https://crm.org/crmland/what-is-a-crm>
- [3]. Nonaka I. (1994). A dynamic theory of organizational knowledge creation. *Organ. Sci.* 5 14–37. 10.1093/fampra/cm098
- [4]. Eby L. T., Allen T. D., Evans S. C., Ng T., DuBois D. L. (2008). Does mentoring matter? A multidisciplinary meta-analysis comparing mentored and non-mentored individuals. *J. Vocat. Behav.* 72 254–267.
- [5]. Polanyi M. (1967). *The Tacit Dimension*. New York, NY: Anchor Books.
- [6]. Borgogni L., Dello Russo S., Petitta L., Latham G. P. (2009). Collective efficacy and organizational commitment in an Italian city hall. *Eur. Psychol.* 14 363–371.
- [7]. Aggarwal, S. (1997). Flexibility management: The ultimate strategy. *Industrial Management*, 39(1), 5–14.
- [8]. Tushman, M. L., & O'Reilly, C. (1997). *Winning through innovation*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press. Comprehend client joint effort.
- [9]. Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. (2003). Understanding customer relationship management (CRM) People, process and technology. *Business Process Management Journal*, 9(5), 672–688.
- [10]. Scullin, S., Allora, J., Lloyd, G. O., & Fjermestad, J. (2002). Electronic customer relationship management: Benefits, considerations, pitfalls and trends. In *Proceedings of the IS One World Conference*, Las Vegas, Nevada, April, pp. 3–5.
- [11]. Romano, A. C. Jr (2000). Customer relations management in information systems research. In H. M. Chung (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Americas Conference in Information Systems (AMCIS)*, Long Beach, California, 10–13 August, pp. 811–819.
- [12]. Sims, D. (2000). A new ROI for new economy CRM and just why doesn't high-tech get it? *crm guru.com*, April 2000.
- [13]. Pohludka, M., Stverkova, H., & Ślusarczyk, B. (2018). Implementation and unification of the ERP system in a global company as a strategic decision for sustainable entrepreneurship. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 1–16.
- [14]. Claycomb, C., Droge, C., & Germain, R. (1999). The effect of just-in-time with customers on organizational design and performance. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 10(1), 37–58.
- [15]. Joo, J. (2007). An empirical study on the relationship between customer value and repurchase intention in Korean internet shopping malls. *The Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 48(1), 53–62.
- [16]. Scullin, S., Allora, J., Lloyd, G. O., & Fjermestad, J. (2002). Electronic customer relationship management: Benefits, considerations, pitfalls and trends. In *Proceedings of the IS One World Conference*, Las Vegas, Nevada, April, pp. 3–5.
- [17]. Epiphany.com. (2001). CRM benefits. Retrieved from http://www.ephany.com/market/crm_benefits.html 2001
- [18]. Waltner, C. (2001). CRM makes on-line shopping personal. *InformationWeek*, January 29, 2001.

- [19]. Rong, G., Wang, M., & Liao, S. (2001). Building an ECRM analytical system with neural network. 2001—Seventh Annual Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS), Boston, Massachusetts, United States, 10–13 August, p. 178.
- [20]. Scullin, S., Allora, J., Lloyd, G. O., & Fjermestad, J. (2002). Electronic customer relationship management: Benefits, considerations, pitfalls and trends. In Proceedings of the IS One World Conference, Las Vegas, Nevada, April, pp. 3–5.
- [21]. Whatis.com. (2001). DIY BI: A guide to self-service business intelligence implementation. Retrieved from http://whatis.techtarget.com/whatis_definition_page/0,4152,211901,00.html
- [22]. Krizanova, A., Gajanova, L., & Nadanyiova, M. (2018). Design of a CRM level and performance measurement model. *Sustainability*, 10(7), 1–17. doi:10.3390/su10072567 .
- [23]. Fidel, P., Schlesinger, W., & Esposito, E. (2018). Effects of customer knowledge management and customer orientation on innovation capacity and marketing results in SMES: The mediating role of innovation orientation. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 22(07), 1850026–1850055.
- [24]. Fidel, P., Schlesinger, W., & Cervera, A. (2015). Collaborating to innovate: Effects on customer knowledge management and performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(7), 1426–1428.
- [25]. Chua, A. Y., & Banerjee, S. (2013). Customer knowledge management via social media: The case of Starbucks. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 17(2), 237–249.
- [26]. Garbarino, E., & Johnson, M. S. (1999). The different roles of satisfaction, trust, and commitment in customer relationships. *Journal of Marketing*, 63(2), 70–87.
- [27]. Molla, A., & Abareshi, A. (2011). Green IT adoption: A motivational perspective. In Proceedings of the 15th Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems, Brisbane, QLD, Australia, 7–11 July; p. 137.
- [28]. Massey, A. P., Montoya-Weiss, M., & Holcom, K. (2001). Re-engineering the customer relationship: Leveraging knowledge assets at IBM. *Decision Support Systems*, 32(2), 155–170.
- [29]. Cohen, W. M., & Levinthal, D. A. (1990). Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35(1), 128–152.
- [30]. Zhu, Z., & Nakata, C. (2007). Reexamining the link between customer orientation and business performance: The role of information systems. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 15(3), 187–203.
- [31]. Menguc, B., & Auh, S. (2006). Creating a firm-level dynamic capability through capitalizing on market orientation and innovativeness. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 34(1), 63–73.
- [32]. Hult, G. T., & Ketchen, D. J. (2001). Does market orientation matter? A test of the relationship between positional advantage and performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(9), 899–906.
- [33]. Dervitsiotis, K. (2010). Developing full-spectrum innovation capability for survival and success in the global economy. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 21(2), 159–170.
- [34]. Soliman, H. S. (2011). Customer relationship management and its relationship to the marketing performance. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(10), 166–182.
- [35]. Ramani, G., & Kumar, V. (2008). Interaction orientation and firm performance. *Journal of Marketing*, 72(1), 27–45.
- [36]. Ru-Jen, L., Chen, R.-H., & Chiu, K.S. (2010). Customer relationship management and innovation capability: An empirical study. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 110(1), 111–133.
- [37]. Gopalakrishnan, S., & Damanpour, F. (1997). A review of innovation research in economics, sociology and technology management. *Omega*, 25(1), 15–66.
- [38]. Huang, D. Y., & Lin, C. Y. (2005). Customer-oriented financial service personalization. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 105(1), 26–44.
- [39]. World Commission on Environment and Development. (1987). *Our common future*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.